

The Role of a Creative Educator in the Educational Process

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Abstract:

The article presents developments in the education process, different views on the role and importance of the creative educator in the world of modern information technology.

Keywords: lesson, speech, pedagogy, creative, pedagogue, inventive, student, education, training.

The rapid development of the world's educational development in images primarily assumes the need for an innovative and creative approach to the educational process. Because it is characterized by an increased need for creativity in each area of human activity, taking place under the influence of innovative-creative creativity, which begets the development and direction of any society in the world. In foreign developed countries, including the United States, Canada, Germany, Russia, Japan, Korea, training processes are carried out on the basis of an innovative-creative approach. The president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev reflected on the urgent tasks that should be carried out in the system of continuing education in the dialogue with public education, higher education employees, expressed a number of thoughts: "... to raise the profile of teachers who are working in educational institutions today, and, on the other hand, the teachers themselves should take a new creative approach to the educational process"[1]. Also, our countryman Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, in his address to the Supreme Assembly on January 24, 2020, also stated that in order to further strengthen the continuity of education, "in our eastern views, education cannot be separated from education and upbringing from education. This requires a great deal of responsibility from today's teacher " [2], he noted.

So, since today's teachers are actively involved in educational work, they are required to organize their activities in harmony with the Times. Primary school teachers operating in public institutions should also have general and special competencies and be able to show creativity in their activities.

It can also be said that a creative educator can in turn look for the most effective way in any situation, any process and at any moment and effectively organize the training process by introducing it into practice, quickly, intelligibly, conveniently, easily and efficiently deliver to the minds of students.

1. Creativity is a pedagogical category that encourages the individual to innovate (innovate).
2. Creative potential is the integration of the professional and personal qualities of the teacher. Because, as long as the teacher is not curious, aspiring by nature, he will never be able to show creativity.
3. Creativity is not a spontaneous quality in teachers, it is due to the fact that the teacher is able to overcome the difficulties faced in the processes of striving for innovations, mastering innovations and being able to apply them in his pedagogical activity, be able to actively, creatively use innovative innovations in his activities and have his own author's ideas, find optimal solutions.

On the basis of the author's approach, the content of the concept of creative potential can be explained as follows: creative potential is an integral part of human spirituality as a category that develops personality and is manifested not in the fact that the personality is a factor of self – development, the basis of personal vitality, the personality is multifaceted in the Creativity potential is closely related to creativity focused on the process of cognition. In the process of mastering professional competencies by teachers in the educational process, the potential for creativity is manifested in the following, in contrast to traditional thinking:

- ✓ Quickness of thinking;
- ✓ Ability to create new ideas;
- ✓ Initiative;
- ✓ Tolerance of uncertainty;
- ✓ To be intelligent;
- ✓ An unusual approach to solving problems.

The scientific essence of the article. Analyzes have shown that self-development and professional success are inextricably linked with the extent to which the ability of creativity in a person has developed.

The development of the creative potential of primary school teachers requires a focus on the following factors that will be necessary in professional pedagogical activity: activity in the creation of new and new ideas; independent study of advanced pedagogical achievements and experiences; exchange of ideas on pedagogical achievements with teachers and colleagues. Necessary qualities creative orientation logical reasoning resourcefulness, work awareness rich imagination possession creative impressiveness and organization full manifestation of their creativity reflexive ability emotional stability new decision-making skills based on existing experience and knowledge each Specialist's self-development and self-expression as a teacher is directly related to his ability to creativeness. The creativity potential of the teacher is reflected as its general characteristic. It is considered the initial condition and result of creative activity. This quality expresses the ability and readiness of the individual to manifest himself. Moreover, on the basis of creative potential, the personal abilities, natural and social capacity of each Specialist are manifested in a holistic way. Creative potential is closely related to creativity focused on the cognitive process.

"Energy" method. This game is very fun and is suitable for more upperclassmen. To prepare for this game, you will need to prepare a number of questions. You can use any questions, whether thematically or to the students themselves.

- Preparation for the game. Write down a list of your questions and print them on paper in A4 format, placing them separately on each line. Then, with the scissors, cut the line between each question. But do not cut to the end of the paper, the questions should be tied together. At the end, stick the questions firmly on the board and also place a litter box closer.
- Play. Form two teams and they must stand in two rows at the very end of the class. The Teacher Said "Go!", when one student from each team runs to the board and rips one of the paper. In doing so, they must read the question on paper aloud and answer the question as soon as possible.
- The fact that this game continues to be fun depends more on the questions. The more interesting and unexpected the questions, the more the game will pass in a way rich in high mood.

Questions for the " energy " method:

- ✓ What is your favorite book or movie?
- ✓ Who do you want to meet more in real life?
- ✓ What is the last event or thing that makes you laugh and laugh?
- ✓ Where do you want to go to relax?
- ✓ What is the best gift you have received?
- ✓ What superpowers would you like to have if you were a superhero?
- ✓ If you were an animal, which animal would you be?
- ✓ Which three things can you not live without?
- ✓ What would you do if you were a king / queen one day?
- ✓ What do you think will be a good teacher?
- ✓ If you have a time machine, what era would you travel to?
- ✓ What do you do when you have free time?

You can also compose questions by adjusting them for yourself and your class. It depends on to what extent you are creative.

3 useful tips for young teachers

Today, a modern teacher should take into account the age of students when teaching effectively, and to teach at the highest level, follow the following 6 Useful Tips:

1. Establish friendly communication with students.

Let students know that you care about them separately. Strengthen all-round contact with them. Let None be left out of sight. Get used to hearing and appreciating each one's feedback, giving them a positive assessment in their place.

2. Create a positive environment when giving knowledge.

Remember, students are always in love with learning in a positive environment. Therefore, try to create an environment in which they can work with their peers. Increase your interest in learning by listening to each student's answer.

3. Use different approaches in the lesson.

According to the researchers, it turns out that younger students are able to concentrate only 10-15 minutes at a time. Therefore, do not exceed one session by 15 minutes. Increase the nonconformity

of classes in the style of play, competition. Be the leader yourself. Then you will not have problems with class management.

As a conclusion, it can be said that today it is advisable not for elementary school teachers to be creative and creative or not, but to organize their professional activities in the spirit of creativity, creativity, to test new ideas in the educational process. The development of creative potential of Primary School students in the educational process requires the following four areas of action:

- 1) Create the necessary conditions for teachers to demonstrate their creative thinking skills and operate freely;
- 2) introduction of an incentive strategy by students to acquire academic subjects with interest;
- 3) to ensure the mastery of the creative approach in finding an innovative approach and pedagogical issue (solution of problems);
- 4) to achieve the expected result by full-fledged implementation of the established educational and educational tasks. Well, the fact that each teacher is able to develop and demonstrate himself, to master professional competencies is directly related to the fact that he has the ability to creativeness. The manifestation of the teacher's creativity activity in all types of pedagogical activity is a requirement of the period. The creativism activity of the teacher forms a general conclusion that it is primarily associated with pedagogical skill.

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